

Automation of Invigilations in College Examination Portal (Exam Click)

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ABSTRACT

Examination Cell is a very confidential and key place for any college. Currently all the activities in the exam cell were mostly including a lot of manual calculations and is slightly making it easier with Open Office or Microsoft Office tools but still there were lot of queries that don't have an exact answer or will take much time to calculate in the exam cell like

- Exam Invigilation's
- Admission / Promotion Lists

To reduce the paper work, we have undertaken this project. The above said problem can be solved by automating the college examination portal. Exam click is an effective tool for integrating efficient, scalable, transparent and robust solutions. The main aim for creating this project is to project the process that undergoes in between exam notification to invigilator remunerations and preparation of admission lists to graduation lists. It has the perspective of attaining attraction of those colleges which don't have better performing software. So, by this project we want to make an attempt, to make the work of the management, exam cell, and department exam cell simple and accurate.

Keywords: Exam Cell, Invigilation, Admission, Exam Portal

I. INTRODUCTION

As our college needs to do the invigilation work, our faculty are undergoing many issues to do the work manually so we want to automate the present process through our project, and make the work easy and

efficient. Open Office or Microsoft Office tools but still there were lot of queries that don't have an exact answer or will take much time to calculate in the exam cell like

- Exam Invigilation's: Preparation of Masterplan for the exams, Exam Invigilation's, Invigilation adjustments, Assigning rooms to the Invigilators, Calculation of Remunerations to the Invigilators at the end to the exams, Calculations of remunerations for other colleges.

- Admission / Promotion Lists: Preparing of admission lists, Attendance Annexures for university which includes condonation and detained lists, preparation of promotion lists.

Our aim of this project is to project the process that undergoes in-between the exam notification to invigilator remunerations and preparation of admission lists to graduation lists. The above said problem can be solved by automating the college examination portal. Exam click is an effective tool for integrating efficient, scalable, transparent and robust solutions. It has the perspective of attaining attraction of those colleges which don't have better performing software. So, by this project we want to make an attempt, to make the work of the management, exam cell, and department exam cells accurate and simple. It reduces the paper work.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Invigilations:

The entire process of assigning invigilation to the faculty involves number of people such as,

- Chief Superintendent
- Exam Section In charge
- Exam Section Staff
- HOD
- Department Exam Section In charge

Exam section consists of exam section incharge and a Data Base. Exam section Incharge sends Request for Login to Data Base, the database then sends request for username, password and then the exam section Incharge enters username, password the database checks the authentication and request for exam details .The exam section incharge enters the exam details and that will be scored in the Data Base, then the database sends the successful message.

Exam section Incharge:

The exam section incharge plays a vital role in assigning the invigilation and involves many activities such as

Master Plan:

The CS gathers all the data related to the exams. The information includes the day, date and time (FN/AN) of the examination. He also gathers the student strength accordingly to the branch and regulation. The information also includes number of rooms and number of invigilators available. The information gathered is sent to the portal.

Division of Invigilators Among Branches:

The given data is abstracted from the portal by the examination section in charge and assigns the invigilators according to the date and time for each branch. The information includes date, time, total no. of invigilators and required branches.

Assigning room numbers:

Consider all the room numbers and give them grades as A,B,C according to the potential of the faculty.

Room wise priority:

The rooms are assigned to the faculty according to a priority. The priority depends on the grading. The given Room wise priority table consists of the floor number, room number and the priority grading. Here, we consider floor as ground, first, second floor. we give room numbers as A ,B ,C. If we select room number as A then in the priority section, the details of A should be displayed. That means if we select a particular room number then in the priority section the selected room number details will be displayed.

Assigning faculty to rooms:

Rooms are assigned according to the grades given to the faculty. Here, we assign a grades to a rooms as A, B, C as well as to a faculty as A, B, C. The rooms are assigned to a faculty according to a potential of a faculty.

HOD-Assigning faculty to invigilation:

The HOD will assign faculty to invigilation in a particular date and time(FN/AN). That means the HOD will select faculty on what time and date, the invigilation should be done.

Invigilation Adjustments:

Here, the Exam Section Incharge / HOD is going to adjust invigilation of a Faculty. Firstly, the year and semester are selected on which a faculty will do invigilation is selected. Then, the date, month, year of a invigilation is selected. The time of a invigilation is selected i.e, FN/AN is selected. The branch of a faculty is selected. When a branch is selected, the selected branch details of a faculty should be displayed. Finally, the faculty is selected.

III. EXISTING WORK

Currently all the activities in the exam cell mostly includes a lot of manual calculations.

- Invigilation details
- Assign faculty to invigilation
- Invigilation report of the day
- Faculty invigilation adjustments

But the main drawbacks of this system include calculations which may result wrong outcomes. And it consumes lot of time to do such work manually. It

may also result in loss of data and is difficult to recreate it. Even sometimes there may be chances of replacement of data by some others which may lead to loss in some way or the other.

IV. PROPOSED WORK

The above said problem can be solved by “Automating the college examination portal”. Exam click is an effective tool for integrating efficient, scalable, transparent and robust solutions. It has the perspective of attaining attraction of those colleges which don't have better performing software. So, by this project we want an attempt to make the work of the management and exam cell itself accurate and simple.

The screen looks as follows:

V. FUTURE ENHANCEMENTS

We can extend our project and develop various other modules which improve the effectiveness of the project. Login module can be developed and we can develop in fields of invigilation and also in remuneration to obtain more results in an efficient manner.

VI. CONCLUSION

Invigilations are the main part of examinations. In this project, the main potential benefit of automating the invigilation adjustments is to reduce errors. This is done in order to eliminate the challenges and limitations of current manual invigilation adjustments. Based on knowledge, it was safely concluded that implementing the proposed system at our college examination section will not only eliminate the challenges faced by college but also provide rich, sound and more flexible environment that will have positive effect on assigning invigilations during exams.

REFERENCES

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